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ANALYSIS OF CURRICULA DEVELOPED FOR PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation. This article analyzes the curricula developed for the subject of physical education in general secondary schools. It proposes theoretical foundations and methods of practical implementation to improve the quality of education in the organization of physical education classes.

Keywords: physical education subject, curriculum, physical education classes, gymnastics, athletics, sports games

In accordance with the tasks defined in the Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4884 dated November 6, 2020, "On additional measures to further improve the education and upbringing system," and No. PP-392 dated November 15, 2024, "On measures to radically improve the teaching of the subject of Physical Education in general secondary schools and develop the professional activities of teachers of this subject," this study defines the main goals, tasks, and system of strategic directions for improving the methodology of teaching "Physical Education" in general secondary schools, taking into account advanced experiences in the republic and global practice.

Physical education is an integral part of human culture and plays an important role in forming a healthy lifestyle. Indeed, the physical education and healthy lifestyle of the younger generation is the guarantee of the nation's health and the foundation of national security.

Physical education classes lay the foundation for the physical development and improvement of motor activity of students, addressing issues regarding the protection of their lives and the improvement of their health.

Physical education is an integral part of the continuous education system in the upbringing of schoolchildren and the rising

younger generation; it is an academic subject that forms vital knowledge, skills, and abilities for developing the motor capabilities of students in general secondary schools.

It defines the theoretical and practical systems, key principles, goals, and tasks for solving current issues in teaching physical education in general secondary educational institutions, as well as the main directions for teaching the subject, including:

- improving the quality of education in accordance with the requirements of the state educational standard for physical education and ensuring compliance with international requirements for personnel training;

- improving the quality of education in the organization of physical education classes;

- ensuring continuity and consistency in the teaching of physical education in general secondary education;

- teaching knowledge in the field of physical education within the curriculum, forming vital motor skills, and shaping a healthy lifestyle for students;

- developing practical skills and abilities regarding regular engagement in physical education and sports, healthy lifestyles, and reproductive health;

- organizing physical culture, mass participation, and sports events;

- implementing the qualification require-

ments for graduates of general secondary educational institutions in the subject of physical education;

using forms, means, and methods aimed at socialization and personal development that possess wide possibilities in the subject of physical education;

introducing assessment criteria based on the competencies defined in the state educational standards;

educating students in general secondary schools based on national and universal human values.

Furthermore, the subject of Physical Education serves to develop physical qualities (strength, speed, agility, endurance, flexibility) by educating students to be physically healthy, mature, and loyal to the homeland; to strengthen students' health; to create conditions for them to grow up physically strong; and to develop skills for proper nutrition in daily life, adherence to personal hygiene rules, and safety regulations during training.

Therefore, analyzing the physical education curricula developed for general secondary schools (for grades 5-9) both abroad and in our country, improving the quality of education in organizing physical education classes, and ensuring continuity and consistency based on a differentiated

approach in teaching physical education are considered some of the urgent problems today. va uzluksizlikni ta'minlash hozirgi kunda dolzarb muammolardan biri hisoblanadi.

The aim of the research is to conduct a comparative analysis of the curricula developed for the subject of physical education in general secondary schools (for students in grades 5-9).

Research tasks:

to conduct a comparative analysis of the physical education curricula and regulatory documents developed for general secondary schools;

to analyze the content and distribution of teaching hours regarding the methodology of teaching sports disciplines across grades 5-9 within the physical education curricula developed for general secondary schools.

Results and discussion. We focused on studying the physical education curriculum for students in grades 5-9 within the program of general secondary schools of the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, based on an analysis.

In the State Educational Standards (SES) for Physical Education and the curriculum of general secondary schools, we can observe that physical education classes for

Table 1

Schedule of distribution of teaching hours by sports disciplines in the physical education curriculum for students in grades 5-9 of general secondary schools under the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

No	Name of sections in the curriculum	Grade V	Grade VI	Grade VII	Grade VIII	Grade IX
Theoretical knowledge		During the lesson process				
1	Gymnastics	14	14	14	12	12
2	Athletics	14	16	16	16	16
3	Sports games (two types of sports are selected based on the school's facilities)	22	20	20	20	20
4	Football	12	12	12	12	12
5	Kurash	4	4	4	6	6
6	Chess	2	2	2	2	2
Total		68	68	68	68	68
Note: Separate hours are not allocated for assessments (control work); they are conducted twice per quarter during the lesson process.						

students in each grade are generally allocated 2 hours per week, amounting to 68 hours per academic year for grades 5-9. See Table 1.

It is established that the physical education curriculum for students in grades 5–9 of general secondary schools includes theoretical and practical training as its main section, as well as the teaching of sports such as athletics, gymnastics, and elements of sports games: basketball, volleyball, handball, football, kurash, and chess.

In the domestic curriculum, 12 hours are allocated for gymnastics classes, which constitutes 12.6% of the total volume of hours; whereas 16, 20, 12, and 6 hours are allocated for athletics, sports games, football, and kurash classes respectively, constituting 23.5%, 29.4%, 17.64%, and 8.82% of the total volume of hours. Considering that each session constitutes an academic hour lasting 45 minutes, a total of 12 hours is allocated to gymnastics. While the program allocates 16 hours to athletics, 20 hours to sports games, 12 hours to football, and 6 hours to kurash classes, only 2 hours per year are allocated to the sport of chess.

In the physical education curriculum specifically intended for students in grades 5–9 of general secondary schools, gymnastics is designated as an active sport; 14 hours (20.58%) are allocated to it, providing wide opportunities for developing children's basic physical skills. The main priority of gymnastics classes is the development of flexibility, as children stretch their muscles and increase their range of motion, thereby reducing the risk of injury.

The ability to maintain balance improves due to the formation of other skills developed through gymnastics tools. Children are asked to maintain equilibrium while controlling coordination on various apparatuses; this is improved to a high degree through gymnastics exercises, as motor activity develops through the performance of complex movements requiring precise coordination of the body and movements.

Athletics is considered the most im-

portant component of the physical education curriculum. It enhances the formation of students' physical fitness, special skills, and emotional well-being. Specifically, it consists of various types of activities ranging from team sports (e.g., basketball, football, volleyball) to individual sports such as athletics, walking, cycling, and swimming. Athletics acquires significant importance in achieving important social priorities by teaching students teamwork, leadership, and communicative skills, as well as by developing a necessary sense of community.

Sports games, including team and individual sports such as basketball, football, volleyball, and tennis, allow for the development of students' physical fitness. Football is considered a high-intensity sport and requires a large amount of equipment and space.

Kurash is a contact sport involving the execution of high-intensity movements that require physical strength and preparation from students. Since kurash is a contact sport, not all students engaging in it may feel comfortable; therefore, to guarantee that all students engage in physical education classes with primary attention focused on safety, it may be required to offer alternative types of activities.

Overall, the physical education curriculum for students in grades 5–9 of general secondary schools is comprised of sports that enhance students' physical fitness, social skills, and emotional comfort.

According to our comparative analysis of foreign and domestic curricula, there is a difference in annual teaching hours in the Russian Federation compared to us: there are 34 more hours in grades 5–9. Specifically, the data shows that in grade 7 there are 28 more hours, and in grades 8–9, up to 25 more teaching hours are provided. Furthermore, such teaching hours in other countries create a foundation for the health level and physical fitness development of the majority of young students, improving their daily healthy lifestyle.

Therefore, increasing the hours in extra-

curricular activities—in addition to the teaching hours provided in our country's physical education curriculum—creates a foundation for shaping the health, physical development, and preparedness of local student youth.

In conclusion, the research results indicate the high importance of the various components of the physical education curriculum—including gymnastics, athletics, sports games, football, and kurash disciplines—in the development of students' general physical fitness. Furthermore, alongside their comprehensive harmonic development, these are considered important factors in developing physical qualities (strength, speed, agility, endurance, flexibility). In particular, among these sports, chess serves to develop their intellectual thinking abilities.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the analysis of educational regulatory documents and curricula, the following conclusions can be noted:

the educational regulatory documents indicate the necessity to review the allocated teaching hours and content within the physical education curriculum of general secondary schools, and to create a subject curriculum that meets the level of standardized requirements;

regarding the standard teaching hours for physical education in the curriculum, it is necessary to teach the techniques of sports disciplines in a phase-by-phase manner and through a sequence of tasks that ensures continuity and consistency, based on the students' age, development, preparedness, and general physical fitness. Only then will we achieve the effectiveness of the lessons.

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